

IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON BUYING DECISION OF RURAL CONSUMERS

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Abstract:

The present Research paper Deals with the study of Impact of Advertising of FMCG products on Rural Consumers (With reference to Nanded District). The study deals with Introduction, Significance of the present Study, objectives, Research Methodology ,Data Analysis and Interpretation and Conclusions.

Key Words: FMCG, Advertising, Brand.

1. Introduction:

Advertising is a growing business in India today. It has been gaining importance in our economy. The role which advertising plays continues to increase in significance year after year. The host of new Products marketed, the expenses and the risk involved in launching them, and the low cost of personal selling are among the conditions which have placed a heavy responsibility on the advertising industry. In India with its growing productive capacity and output, there is need for finding consumers for this growing output. Advertising plays an important role in the process of moving the goods from the producer to the consumers with mass marketing to distribute the output of our production. The gross National product may increase mass marketing while aiding the consumers to choose from amongst the variety of products offered for his selection. It was only in the latter half of the 19th century, that mass advertising as we know it today came into being. Mass Production became a reality and channels of distribution had to be developed to cope with the

physical movement of goods, creating a need for mass communication to inform consumers of the choices available to them. This development was accelerated by increasing Literacy. In India advertising as a crucial and recognized means of promotion was accepted 25 years ago this delay is obviously attributable late industrialization in our country.

2. Significance of the present study:

Advertising by facilitating mass production and distribution has provided immense employment opportunities to people. It is responsible for creating and delivering rising standard of living people. It has made possible tremendous industrialization and economic development in many countries. It is the backbone of modern national and international marketing. The Present study Impact of advertising of FMCG Products on rural consumer is basically to study the rural consumer's behavior while dealing with FMCG Products and advertising impact of FMCG products on rural consumers buying behavior. The rural population is nearly three times the urban, so the rural consumer became prime target of marketer's. Increased literacy and awareness in rural market created new demands for daily consumption products. This observed mostly in rural consumers because of the advertising effect of marketer's through the Television, Radio, Newspapers, Billboards, Hoardings and other modes of advertising.

3. Objectives of the study:

Following are the specific objectives of the study.

- 1) To Study the profile of selected rural consumers in Nanded District.
- 2) To examine the Impact of advertising on rural consumers behavior in Nanded District

3.1. Research Methodology:

The required data for this research study was collected from primary as well as secondary sources. Primary data was collected from respondents by visiting personally and secondary data was collected from books, journals, magazines, newspapers, report and extensive use of internet.

3.2. Methods of Sample Selection:

3.2.1) Selection of Talukas. There are 16 Talukas in Nanded district, outof them 8 Talukas have been selected as Sample through convenience or purposive non random sampling method. The selection of Talukas is based on following parameters

- 1) As per the sub divisional offices.
- 2) Location Wise.
- 3) Demographic Wise.
- 4) Socio- economic condition of talukas.

3.2.2) Sample size:

It is essential that the individual included in the survey are representative of the total population from which they have taken. This helps to generalize the findings of the population as a whole for the present study the researcher has taken total sample size of 400. Larger the sample size generally lead to increase the precision estimating unknown parameters of sample size. The sample selected as Follows

3.3.3) Selection of the respondent:

For the purpose of selecting rural consumers convenience sampling method has been used, total sample size for present study was 400 consumers, the sample consist of talukas Ardhapur, Bhokar, Biloli, Degloor, Dharmabad, Hadgaon, Loha and Kinwat.

4. Data Analysis and interpretation:

This chapter aims to analyzing the collected data. It gives the analysis of advertising impact of FMCG products on rural consumer's behavior. It also gives the allocation of advertising awareness of rural consumers, Different media habits of rural consumer's with regard to Selected FMCG products, different factors affecting rural consumer behavior and their brand preference while purchasing FMCG products.

Table No.1
Impact of Advertisement on buying decision of Rural Consumers

Sr. No.	Variable	Consumers	Percentage %
1	Yes	287	71.75%
2	No	113	28.25%
Total		400	100%

(Field Survey)

In the above analysis table researcher analyzed the impact of advertising on buying decision of rural consumer's, 71.75% rural consumer's said that advertising significantly affect their buying decision and 28.25% rural consumers are opined that advertising did not affect their buying decision.

Conclusion:

The impact of advertising on rural consumer's is determined by the effectiveness of advertising and the effectiveness of advertising depends on factors like design of ads which can catch the heart of consumer's and selection of appropriate media vehicle all multiple media options for complete reinforcement of promotional campaign. As the study very clearly stated impact of advertising can be positive and negative positive impact as a long lasting impact which further improves the goodwill of the company and product range as a whole. It gives the reinforcement to the personnel selling activities where the companies spend sizable amount of money and manpower. Designing the ad focusing the right segment of consumers makes it convenient for advertiser on one hand and makes the life of the consumer also very easy on the other.

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